

The Metamorphosis of Products: a Sustainable Design Strategy That Favours Increased Attachment

LALANDE, Philippe, École de design industriel, Université de Montréal, c.p.6128, succursale, Centre-ville, Montréal, QC H3C 3J7, Telephone (514) 343 7911, Fax (514) 343 5694, philippe.lalande@umontreal.ca

RACINE, Martin, Department of Design and Computation Arts, Concordia University
1455, De Maisonneuve boulevard west, Montréal, QC H3G 1M8, Telephone (514) 848 2424
ext. 4656, Fax (514) 848, mracine@alcor.concordia.ca

FULL PAPER

CONFERENCE THEME: Attachment and Behavior

Abstract

With the rapid change of consumer trends and the evolution of technology, users are losing the emotional attachment they used to have with their belongings. At an increasing rate, people replace their products, even if still fully functional. The idea of throwaway consumption is now spreading to “hard” consumer goods: computers and electronic apparatus, leisure equipment, domestic appliances, etc. and this is having disastrous effects on the environment. How can this make sense in the perspective of sustainable development? This paper describes the Metamorphosis approach: a strategy based on the idea that objects could change and evolve through time, thus promoting stronger emotional ties with their owners who would be less inclined to throw them away.

A number of experiments were conducted, showing that Rapid Prototyping technology can be used to transform and modify products. The first phase of this project focused on giving new life to products that are usually discarded. In the second phase, the research team designed objects from scratch – a number of lamps – while anticipating a second life from the initial stages of the design process. The various projects are described and show the potential of the Metamorphosis strategy as a new tool for sustainable design.

Keywords: Industrial design, eco-design, recycling, emotions and cognition

Introduction

Our society of consumption leads us to replace the products we use more and more frequently. At an increasing rate, new models appear with appealing designs and colours, tempting us to buy the latest “new and improved” product. Moreover, contrary to the way objects were built in the past, many of today's products are no longer designed to be repaired. But even still fully functional, we are urged to replace products to access new features and the latest technology¹. These marketing strategies have undermined the development of long-term attachment between products and their users.

The passionate early stages of a subject-object relationship could be described as a honeymoon period, a period of intense synergy within which everything is new, interesting and the consumption of one another is feverish (...) During recent years, consumers have become serial honeymooners, and today subject-object relationships are less marriage, more one-night stand.(Chapman, 2005)

While this can be viewed as a by-product of materialism in our society (Kasser, 2002), it cannot be denied that technology's rapid evolution is promoting premature obsolescence. The idea of throwaway consumption is now spreading to “hard” consumer goods: computers and electronic apparatus, leisure equipment, domestic appliances, etc. This phenomenon makes sense for an economy based on endless production and consumption, but concern is growing over its disastrous effects on the environment. How can this make sense in the perspective of sustainable development? Instead of consuming less materials and energy, it appears that the current trend is leading us in the opposite direction, towards more pollution and more waste.

One of the most popular current strategies for reversing this trend focuses on recycling, encouraged by environmental policy but also economical potential. While recycling is no doubt a positive environmental strategy, especially for packaging, several environmentalists and designers have nevertheless pointed out its limits:

Ecodesign limits itself to an environmental technological approach and recycling is sometimes even an excuse for more rapid discarding (Van Hinte, 1997).

¹ Replacing a functioning television set with a new flat screen model is a convincing example of this trend.

Researchers focusing on ecology also remain critical about recycling and consider that it does nothing to curb the prevalent throwaway attitude. Their goal is to strengthen the long-term relationships with products and promote the idea of *sustainment*:

A sustainment is much more about extending the life of existing products, than it is about reducing the ecological impact of our wastefulness. Re-using materials and products delivers much more substantial sustainments than recycling (The EcoDesign Foundation, 2004)

In this perspective, keeping products longer appears to be an effective strategy for sustainability. However, its implementation is opposed by several market forces: the world changes, technology evolves, new trends appear, factors that weigh heavily on the life span of products. To favour durability, we need to consider what Chapman (2005) calls “emotionally durable design” and consider that many people rid themselves of fully functional objects because they lack empathy for them. Another researcher (Norman, 2005) has proposed that the relationship between a product and its owner takes place on three levels: visceral, behavioural and reflective and that designers need to condition the emotional impact of products on these three levels in order to favour their longevity. This means that objects must be designed differently, favouring durability and the qualities that promote meaningful long-term relationships with their owners. But certain questions arise: What strategies can be used to create a long-term level of attachment between consumers and their products? How can the excitement of product ownership be maintained on the long term? How can technology be used to transform and renew products during their life span?

The research presented in this paper is a follow-up to a wider reflection on sustainability and design investigating the potential of a technology named Rapid Prototyping (RP) to produce more durable products. RP allows for the fabricating of objects directly from computer generated 3D files. Included under the RP banner are technologies that can produce complex shapes automatically, that is without tooling or human intervention, using raw materials in some initial shapeless form (powder, sheet, fluid, etc.) (Burns, 1993). This first research effort was focussed on the application of RP to the repair and replacement of broken parts (see www.precoc.ca). Other studies have explored the potential of RP to build products tailored to a user’s individual needs and preferences and the impacts of this personalization on the attachment felt for these products (Auclair, 2005). In the context of sustainability and the need to design products that foster increased emotive attachment with their owners, this current re-

search looks at how RP can be used to create objects that can evolve over time, somewhat like the way software can be updated through successive versions by replacing or adding code. This strategy labelled Metamorphosis aims to develop and preserve attachment by giving a further life to products whose aesthetic appeal has faded, or whose technology has become outdated. Other than the analogy to software, this research was also inspired by certain principles of bionic design (Coineau and Kresling, 1987): various manifestations of metamorphosis found in nature as, for example, caterpillars that become butterflies or snakes that periodically replace their skin. By exploring how to design objects by anticipating their eventual transformation through the use of RP, it was hoped to stimulate new type of relationship with objects as they evolve through time, providing their owners with fresh and exciting experiences, in accordance with Chapman's perspective:

To avoid such wasteful obsolescence, products must mutually evolve alongside users, sustaining value by revealing their true beauty only through the slow passing of time.
(Chapman, 2005)

Method

This research was motivated primarily by the need to experiment with tangible products, bridging theory to practice, and to define the potential and the limits of the Metamorphosis strategy. Rapid Prototyping was used to fabricate or modify different objects. The results were then evaluated and analysed, in order to validate the feasibility of applying Metamorphosis to other products. The experiments were carried out at the research laboratories of the Institute for Research/Creation in Media Arts and Technologies – Hexagram. All Rapid Prototyping was produced using fused deposition modelling (FDM) technology, and rigid ABS plastic resin. This research was done in the context of academia with the collaboration of a team of six research assistants from two Universities².

Phase 1: The Metamorphosis of existing products

The objective of this first phase was to test the Metamorphosis strategy on a number of existing objects. A first series of products consisted of ball-point pens and children markers. These objects are available in abundance in schools, day care centres and office environments, and

² The team was composed of Jean-François Allie, Martin Faubert and Alexandre Joyce from the Université de Montreal and Ruwayna Ghanem, Andre Arnold and Miruna Radulescu from Concordia University.

typically thrown away after use³. Such single-use products generate very little emotional attachment with their owners; they are inexpensive and their users do not mind discarding them and renewing their collection. Another reason for this choice of product was their relatively simple geometry and standard dimensions.

A second exercise consisted of attempting to apply the Metamorphosis strategy to a larger product, of more complex geometry and construction: a ThermosTM vacuum bottle.

Validation of Phase 1

In order to validate the potential for applying Metamorphosis on a larger number of object, an experiment was run: a 'Metamorphosis' project was proposed to a class of 60 students in the Industrial Design program at the University of Montreal. The objective was to evaluate the level of enthusiasm and creativity that Metamorphose could stimulate with potential users. Each team of three students were asked to choose a product from a list of four and challenged to propose its transformation into another. The products listed were a pair of swimming goggles, a computer mouse, a toothbrush and a flashlight. These objects were chosen for their relatively short life span, their poor adaptation to recycling and their small size (as imposed by the dimensional limits of the RP machine). The project was presented to the class as a competition, the winners having their concepts produced.

Phase 2 – Anticipating the Metamorphosis of new objects

The second phase of this research was to develop new products from scratch, anticipating their potential transformations. A common theme for the exercise was to design a domestic lighting device. It was felt to offer an appropriate level of challenge while presenting the opportunity of integrating low energy light sources such as LEDs and compact fluorescent lamps.

³ Markers and pens are very difficult to recycle because the barrel is sealed off with a welded cap, preventing the removal of the ink tube.

Results

Phase 1 - Metamorphosis of existing objects

a) Disposable ball-point pen

The objective of this exercise was to propose ways of reusing as much as possible of a ball-point pen's geometry and reconfiguring it to satisfy a new need. The particular model, a BIC Round Stic™ ball-point pen, was chosen for its simple unadorned geometry and its ability to represent the typical throwaway product (figure 1).

Figure 1 - BIC Round Stic™ ball-point pen

From the outset, in view of the simple nature of the product, the approach was, rather than attempting to modify the product itself, to use it in multiple copies as a building element in a construction system. The proposals focussed on reusing the pen barrels as vertexes of a construction system by assembling multiple barrels into various geometrical formations with the use of RP produced joints (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Three of the many types of RP produced joints for BIC pens

The large number of joint configurations that were developed allowed for a variety of types of construction, from simple, planar configurations to more complex structures (figure 3).

Figure 3 - A selection of complex shapes constructed with RP produced joints

b) Disposable felt tip marker

Of similar geometry to the first, two versions of Crayola™ washable ink felt tip markers were explored, the fine-line, pencil format marker (Figure 4), and the larger, full-size version (Figure 5). Here again, the objective was to transform this product into a construction toy.

Figure 4 - Fine-line Crayola™

Figure 5 - Full-size Crayola™

All concepts relied on RP produced joints to assemble the markers into geometric structures. Several concepts were proposed and demonstrated, including not only end-to-end assemblies, but also vertex-to-vertex and end-to-vertex assemblies (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Various joining configurations made possible with RP produced joint

This experimentation was judged very promising in terms of the objectives of the project. RP showed its potential to produce parts that ideally fit to existing products and give it a new life as an exciting construction system. Moreover, the secondary function is complementary to the initial nature of the product and draws attention to the physical properties of the marker,

which enable it to be more than a simple expendable and temporary container for coloured ink, thus extending the life of an otherwise wasteful product.

c) Thermos bottle

Finally, a third product of entirely different morphology was chosen, a disused Thermos™ vacuum bottle. Three proposals were delivered, two of which were based on the transformation of the vacuum bottle into a lighting fixture. The first, needing the RP production of two parts (figure 7) which, when assembled with the parts of the existing product, transformed it into a child's castle lamp (figure 8).

Figure 7 - RP parts required

Figure 8 - Castle lamp

The second proposal required the production of three parts which, when assembled with the Thermos™, turned it into a portable camping or patio light (Figures 9 and 10).

Figure 9 - One of the RP produced parts

Figure 10 - Camping/patio light

Finally, the third proposal took the Metamorphosis approach into an entirely new direction, proposing the transformation of a primarily functional product into a whimsically personalized effigy, becoming above all a decorative artefact (figure 11).

Figure 11 - Transformation of a Thermos™ vacuum bottle with added RP produced parts.

The examples shown here demonstrate that it is possible to imagine new vocations for existing products that appear to have reached the end of their useful life. Due to the flexibility of Rapid Prototyping technology and the nature of the transformations required, they can actually be user defined. This is seen as a potential means of strengthening the attachment between users and the products they own and, consequently, the motivation to keep them.

The Validation of Phase 1

The work done in Phase 1 served not only to shed light on the technical feasibility of the Metamorphosis approach. We questioned the Metamorphosis strategy and the means by which users could discover the potential for consumer products to evolve. We also explored some of the economic, social and creative imperatives that might drive Metamorphosis. As a means of handling this questioning, we postulated a scenario whereby consumer products could be distributed on a similar principle as Open Source programming. That is, that a product's 'Source Code' is made public by its manufacturer as a means of tapping into the design community's creative potential and benefit from the distributed resources of a web-based creative pool. As a first means of validating the potential of this resource, we proposed a Metamorphosis project to a group of sixty 2nd year industrial design students. Working in teams of three, each team was asked to propose a second life for one of four, previously defined, products: a toothbrush, a computer mouse, a flashlight and a pair of swimming goggles.

The group was given two weeks to complete the exercise, and hand in their proposal in the form of 3D computer files of RP parts needed to modify the existing product as well as computer images of the completed transformation.

The results were very encouraging and eloquently demonstrated that the potential for renewal of a product's appeal through re-formatting is present. We present two examples from the twenty proposals submitted (Figures 12 and 13).

Figure 12 - Swimming goggle to cycle light Figure 13 - Flashlight to candle holder

Phase 2 - Anticipating the Metamorphosis of new objects

Finding ways of transforming existing objects and giving them fresh purpose is a challenging task that calls for creativity and ingenuity. This seems to come, at least in part, from the fact that the products we experimented with were never designed for any other purpose than that for which they were originally proposed. We suggest, therefore, that the Metamorphosis strategy encouraging long-term attachment can more easily and effectively be applied to products at their inception.

During the second phase of the project, the research team applied itself to conceiving a number of lighting fixtures that would embody the seeds of their future transformations. The anticipated evolution of the product from its initial format could be of various natures, from a complete change of vocation to the ability of offering various options or variants.

A total of six lamps were designed and built. It is interesting to note that not all proposals embodied the same concept of Metamorphosis. In some cases, an evolution was proposed, envisioning that the product would follow a more or less smooth transition from its original state into successive versions of the same product (figure 14).

Figure 14 - A customizable lamp that can take on a great number of successive configurations. Through this approach, the initial design of the object can evolve, according to its owner, who adds or removes patterns, giving different forms to the lamp. Owners could also create custom elements, for even greater personalization.

A particularly interesting variant of this approach is evident in the concept of a light fixture made primarily out of the water-soluble support material, which is a by-product of RP production and normally removed as part of the production process. This concept can therefore be "dissolved" into successive states to produce varied effects as it ages (figure 15).

Figure 15 - Experimental lamp made of dissolvable RP resin

This innovative process results in an unusual texture, and expresses the metaphor of an object that is slowly fading away. Eventually, the frame can be totally dissolved and replaced by a different one, of a totally new form, according to the owner's taste.

An approach explored in two separate concepts also involves the user in configuring the initial product. In both cases, the user contributes parts from his, or her own environment, to complete the RP produced components.

Figure 16 - Lamp composed of various parts, some of which can be provided by the user

The lamp in this example (Figure 16) is 'designed for disassembly' (DFD); all the components can be interchanged using various materials. Here, the mast is a bamboo stick, the contour of the head can be designed by the owner and produced by RP. Finally, the user cuts out translucent material of his/her choice and inserts it in the RP 'ring'.

Figure 17 - Lamp's structure is RP produced and completed with user-supplied fill material

The example in Figure 17 allows the owner to change the geometry of the contour structure (the four arms) and generate a totally different lamp (from concave to convex if we flip the arms). Changing only certain elements of the structure allows the creation of a new lamp, without having to replace it after its first life.

One light was designed with a light shade defined by the random generation of NURBS curves on the surface of a domed cone. The resulting swirling geometry is particularly well

adapted to other aesthetic applications such as that of a decorative fruit bowl (figure 18). From the initial stage of the creation of this lamp, a base was planned that would fit snugly in the top of the lamp shade.

Figure 18 - Lamp's elegant swirls are well adapted to becoming a semitransparent fruit bowl

A more complex approach was employed in the proposal of a light fixture, which could contribute to giving further life to a second product: cellular phones. Millions of these are discarded each year and this concept places them at the heart of a desk lamp, powering a single high intensity light emitting diode. Incorporating RP produced custom fittings, the lamp houses the defunct cellular and feeds off its battery and power supply (figure 19).

Figure 19 - The base of this adjustable lamp houses a disused cellular phone for power

It is interesting to see how the lamp takes on a few of the characteristics of the metamorphosed object: its compactness, its portability and of course, it's rechargeable.

Conclusions

This project explored ways of designing products that promote stronger links of emotional attachment with their users. As Donald Norman pointed out recently (Norman and Stening, 2006), commitment and love for the things we own can best be developed by personalization - making them our own. We also know that products that are more strongly cherished and appreciated won't be discarded and replaced so frequently. This represents a potential lessening of the environmental impacts caused by recycling, waste disposal, the extraction and transformation of raw materials and the manufacturing of new products.

The Metamorphosis approach that was explored can be evaluated on two levels. At the first level, it can be seen as an incremental improvement over other strategies for reducing the environmental cost incurred by our economic system based on endless consumption. Traditional recycling reduces discarded products to their component materials, which are then reintroduced into the production chain as raw materials, which can be processed into new products. Since products are rarely designed in view of optimal material recovery, this type of recycling very often produces a loss in materials quality and severely limits the number of cycles that a material can be recycled before having to be discarded.

William McDonough and Michael Braungart argue for an approach called eco-effectiveness (McDonough and Braungart, 2002) whereby products are designed to allow for material recycling with minimal or no down-grading, permitting perpetual retrieval and re-use.

Metamorphosis takes this last approach one step further. In Phase I, new uses were explored for existing products while in Phase II, a number of new products were proposed, relying on various techniques that would allow them to be recycled into new variations, adaptations or entirely different products with a minimal investment of new material. This type of recycling draws its effectiveness from the reuse not only of a product's materials, but of a number of other dimensions of its manufactured essence: geometry, colour, surface finish, mechanical properties and, in some cases, technical empowerment. The experiments conducted in this project demonstrate that this is possible, albeit with much more ease when designing products from scratch.

This first level holds promise for a gain in ecological effectiveness, and has shown the feasibility of Metamorphose and its potential to rejuvenate objects. But Metamorphosis also acts on a second level: beyond giving old products new life, Metamorphosis calls on the user to play an active role in making the product evolve. This, in turn, promises to enhance the commitment felt by users for the products they own and the attachment that will retard the decision to discard and replace. While this study did not attempt to evaluate this chain of effects, the results obtained here suggest that such an investigation would be valuable.

The Metamorphosis strategy for product evolution relies heavily on Rapid Prototyping (RP) technology. While RP has made great advances in recent years, it is a technology that is still in its infancy, being commercially available since less than fifteen years. This research was conducted using a Titan Rapid Prototyping machine from Stratasys inc., which uses a technique called Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM). The parts it produces are made of rigid ABS plastic having physical properties roughly equivalent to 60% to 80% of those of injection moulded ABS (Grimm, 2003). While this is sufficient for most non-critical applications, there are cases where failure can occur within the RP produced part. There are also other limitations inherent in present-day RP technology such as surface finish, choice of colours, degree of transparency, flexibility, maximum part size and cost, all of which will need to be addressed before the Metamorphosis strategy put forth in this research could become viable. However, RP technologies are advancing rapidly. Since the beginning of this research, new materials have been introduced, existing models have been improved, new models have been added and new methods for improving surface finish have been demonstrated. The future of the RP industry is considered to be very promising (Wohlers, 2005). It is believed that use of automated production technologies such as RP will increase dramatically as costs drop and quality approaches what we now associate with mass-produced products.

There are, of course, limits that present-day RP technology will not overcome: the inability to replace a product's technical components. For this reason, all the products chosen for this research were technically simple. The products we use in our daily lives, however, are becoming increasingly complex and applying Metamorphosis will need new technologies complementary to RP. This is precisely what M.I.T. researcher Neils Gershenfeld envisions. His Personal Electro Mechanical Systems (PEMS) fabricator is an RP machine that builds technical components and assemblies used to make personalized complex products, ranging from toys to appliances (Gershenfeld, 1999). Whether or not this technology can be made simple, small

and inexpensive enough to be located in the home, it could nevertheless be applied to the updating of complex technical products.

Designing products that can evolve demands a great deal of creativity. The six lamps of Phase II required considerable concentration and ingenuity to develop. In spite of this, all would require considerably more time and effort to bring to a state of commercial viability. A way of bringing more creative energy to bear on the generation of transformable products would be to rethink the way products are supported once they reach the marketplace. Based on the model of Open Source software development, manufacturers would publish the 3D computer files describing their products' physical configurations. Tapping the vital energies of society's creative communities, proposals would then be sought for ways of modifying and improving these products, ranging from incremental adaptations to radical re-affectation. The results could be offered either as a non-profit community service or on the basis of a commercial venture, returning licensing revenue to both the product's original manufacturer and the designer of the proposed modifications. The results of the student project at the end of Phase I were sufficiently encouraging to suggest further study in this direction.

Metamorphosis is a strategy for designing products that users will want to keep. This first research effort has suggested some ways that this can be done and demonstrated Metamorphosis' potential for becoming a viable addition to the designer's toolbox. It is hoped that further research in this direction will bring about a positive change in the way consumers relate to the products they use.

Bibliography

- AUCLAIR, I. (2005) L'influence des techniques de modélisation 3D et de prototypage rapide sur la personnalisation d'objet en design industriel. *Faculté de l'aménagement*. Montréal, Université de Montréal.
- BURNS, M. (1993) *Automated Fabrication: Improving Productivity in Manufacturing*, Englewood Cliffs, PTR Prentice Hall.
- CHAPMAN, J. (2005) *Emotionally Durable Design: Objects, Experiences and Empathy*, 2005, Earthscan Publications.
- COINEAU, Y. & KRESLING, B. (1987) *Les inventions de la nature et la bionique*, Paris, Hachette.
- GERSHENFELD, N. (1999) *When Things Start To Think*, New York, Henry Holt and Company.
- GRIMM, T. (2003) Fused Deposition Modeling: A Technology Evaluation. IN T. A. GRIMM AND ASSOCIATES, I. (Ed.) Edgewood, Kentucky.
- KASSER, T. (2002) *The High Price of Materialism*, London, M.I.T. Press.
- MCDONOUGH, W. & BRAUNGART, M. (2002) *Cradle to Cradle: Remaking the Way We Make Things*, New York, North Point Press.
- NORMAN, D. A. (2005) *Emotional Design: Why We Love (or Hate) Everyday Things*, New York, Basic Books.
- NORMAN, D. A. & STENING, B. (2006) Up Close and Personal With Emotional Design. *Curve Magazine*.
- THE ECODESIGN FOUNDATION (2004) http://www.edf.edu.au/Sustainments/What_are/WhatAreNotMain.htm. Sydney, Society For Responsible Design. Visited on 10 April 2006
- VAN HINTE, E. (1997) *Eternally Yours: Visions on Product Endurance*, Amsterdam, 010 Publishers.
- WOHLERS, T. (2005) *Wohlers Report 2005*, Fort Collins, Wohlers Associates.